

Supplementary Materials

Keystone Epitope Theory: Implications for Hypersensitivity, Autoimmunity, and Transplantation

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S1. Glossary

pHLA (peptide–HLA). The peptide–HLA complex on the cell surface, read by CD8 TCRs and, in some contexts, by NK receptors via KIR and NKG2.

TRM (tissue-resident memory T cell). A memory T-cell population that persists in tissues and responds rapidly in situ without recruitment from blood.

Modified self-ligand. A self-derived pHLA complex perceived as non-self because the peptide repertoire is altered by a drug or post-translational modification.

Heterologous immunity. Prior pathogen-specific memory shapes responses to an unrelated antigen, often via TCR cross-reactivity.

Public / private TCR. Public TCR solutions are shared across multiple individuals; private TCRs are individual-specific.

NPV / PPV. Negative and positive predictive value. Low PPV under strong HLA associations implies additional necessary conditions beyond HLA.

ERAP. Endoplasmic reticulum aminopeptidases shape which peptides are available for HLA class I presentation.

Keystone organism / epitope. As used in this review: a persistent, niche-structured pathogen (e.g., CMV, EBV, HSV) whose conserved epitopes seed durable, tissue-positioned T-cell memory through repeated antigenic stimulation ³.

S2. Supplementary Table S1

Supplementary Table S1. Operational features used in this review to characterize persistent organisms and their epitopes. This is a heuristic summary, not a formal taxonomy.

Feature	Organism level	Epitope level
Chronic persistence and reactivation	Establish lifelong latency with intermittent reactivation	Sustain durable T-cell memory through periodic antigenic restimulation
Tissue/niche restriction	Seed TRM in defined niches (e.g., HSV at dermal–epidermal junction, EBV in lymphoid tissue, CMV in vascular endothelium)	Presented in anatomical contexts that shape compartment-specific immune coordination
Host-regulated viral burden	Viral DNA burden is a measurable, host-regulated trait shaped by antigen processing and MHC genotype ^{8 9}	Constrained by host peptide-processing machinery (ERAP1/2, LNPEP, tapasin)
Functionally constrained targets	Organisms for which immune escape mutations carry a replicative fitness cost	Epitopes where amino acid substitution impairs viral fitness, favoring durable immune targeting

S3. Evidence for Herpesvirus-Associated Heterologous Immunity

Persistent herpesvirus infections have been associated with enhanced immune responses to unrelated pathogens. CMV-seropositive individuals show augmented CD8+ T-cell effector function in response to heterologous viral antigens such as influenza ⁵⁷. HSV-1 infection in mice primes tissue-resident CD8+ T cells that enhance resistance at barrier sites ⁵⁸ and may create a Th1-skewed cytokine environment ⁵⁹. CD4+ regulatory T cells primed during HSV-1 infection can modulate responses to subsequent infections ⁶⁰, and prior HSV infection enhances skin dendritic-cell mobilization ⁶¹.

These effects are contingent on timing and host genetic context. They are consistent with, but do not prove, the hypothesis that persistent herpesviruses contribute to broader immune calibration.

S4. NK Cell–HLA Coordination

A single pHLA complex can be read by both CD8 T cells (via TCR) and NK cells (via KIR and CD94–NKG2 receptors). Peptide-specific engagement of NK-cell inhibitory and activating receptors tunes NK-cell responses depending on the precise HLA-peptide combination ⁶². Changes in the presented peptide repertoire—from viral adaptation, drug exposure, or altered processing— can differentially affect CTL and NK thresholds. Loss of CTL visibility through HLA downregulation may simultaneously disinhibit NK cells, and vice versa. This dual-reading architecture helps explain why some drug-altered peptidomes trigger

CTL-mediated injury without disinhibiting NK cells, and why KIR/HLA genotype modifies disease risk and severity.

S5. Structural Basis for TCR Cross-Reactivity

TCR cross-reactivity is relatively common, reflecting the high frequency of shared TCR clonotypes across individuals and the structural constraints on TCR diversity⁶³. Many TCRs recognize multiple structurally similar but distinct epitopes, including pathogen-derived antigens and self-peptides modified by drugs or post-translational modifications. Immune tolerance mechanisms regulate most cross-reactive interactions, but virus-specific TCRs that form part of a tissue-positioned memory response may be activated by mimicking ligands that breach local regulatory thresholds.

Herpesvirus-specific TCR clonotypes have been reported to cross-react with modified self-antigens^{6 63}. Many herpesvirus-derived peptides are longer than typical CD8+ T-cell epitopes (8–12 amino acids) and protrude from the MHC class I binding groove⁶⁴. Structural studies of EBV epitopes show that such protruding peptides require TCRs capable of conformational adaptation upon recognition⁶⁴. This mode of recognition may contribute to the capacity of herpesvirus-trained TCRs to cross-react with modified self-peptides sharing a similar conformational footprint.

S6. IgE-Mediated Allergy vs T Cell–Mediated Hypersensitivity

IgE-mediated allergies and T cell–mediated drug hypersensitivity differ in their mechanisms and clinical trajectories. IgE-mediated food and drug allergies typically arise from disrupted mucosal tolerance and are often short-lived, route-dependent, and amenable to desensitization^{65 66 67 68 69}. T cell–mediated hypersensitivity, by contrast, may arise when drug-modified peptides engage preexisting, tissue-positioned memory T cells originally trained on persistent viral epitopes. Because these effectors are maintained by ongoing viral surveillance rather than classical peripheral tolerance, the resulting responses can be durable⁴. This distinction may be relevant to clinical counseling: IgE-mediated reactions involve route and barrier considerations, whereas T cell–mediated reactions involve HLA genotype, tissue niche, and prior viral exposure.

S7. Detailed Keratinocyte Evidence in SJS/TEN

Upon sustained exposure to an offending drug that binds non-covalently to an endogenous peptide, keratinocytes expressing the risk HLA class I molecule can process and present this modified self-peptide, activating pre-existing CD8+ TRM in the skin. This illustrates the non-covalent, drug-dependent recognition route to Signal 1 and contrasts with covalent haptentation and with abacavir-like repertoire alteration (Figure S2). Activation may proceed with reduced reliance on de novo priming when sufficient drug-dependent Signal 1, together with tissue context, breaches local inhibitory thresholds.

Once activated, these CD8+ TRM recognize and target keratinocytes presenting drug neoepitopes via the risk HLA allele. This leads to widespread keratinocyte apoptosis and subsequent epidermal necrolysis, as well as damage to other mucosal surfaces, including corneal epithelium, oral mucosa, and genital tract⁴⁰. This is consistent with why the disease is severe, localized to drug-exposed epithelial surfaces, progresses rapidly even after drug discontinuation, and can recur upon re-exposure years later.

S8. Exposure Timing: Selected Observations and Caveats

Selected cohort studies report associations between early herpesvirus acquisition and reduced rates of allergic and autoimmune disease. In the Rhea cohort (Greece), children seropositive for multiple herpesviruses by age 6 were less likely to develop eczema⁷⁰. In the Generation R cohort (Netherlands), children with serological evidence of prior CMV, EBV, or HSV-1 infection were less likely to test positive for transglutaminase type 2 antibodies, a marker of celiac autoimmunity⁷¹. In comparative studies of farming

communities, children raised in higher-exposure settings show lower rates of asthma and allergic sensitization than genetically similar children in lower-exposure settings^{72 73}. Epidemiologic associations between delayed EBV acquisition and increased MS risk are well documented^{45 46}, though the causal pathway is not resolved.

Caveats. These observations are associative, not proof of causation. Multiple confounders (diet, household size, antibiotic use, microbial diversity) covary with the timing of herpesvirus acquisition. The overwhelming population-level benefits of improved sanitation, vaccination, antibiotics, safer childbirth, shelter, and nutrition are not in question. Any exposure-timing hypothesis concerns rare immune tradeoffs among individuals who survive and thrive under modern conditions. Autoimmune disease and drug hypersensitivity remain minority outcomes requiring additional genetic and immunological gates beyond exposure timing alone.

S9. Experimental Validation: Workflow Details and Animal-Model Limits

S9.1 Lesion-to-mechanism workflow

Figure 6 in the main text summarizes this lesion-to-mechanism workflow schematically; the steps below expand that logic in prose.

The central prediction is that T-cell clonotypes enriched at the site of drug hypersensitivity cross-recognize both the drug-modified self-peptide and a viral peptide presented by the same HLA allele. Testing this requires a staged workflow:

1. **Lesion-enriched clonotype identification.** Single-cell TCR sequencing of T cells from the active lesion (e.g., blister fluid in SJS/TEN, skin biopsy in DRESS) identifies oligoclonally expanded TCR $\alpha\beta$ pairs.
2. **Cognate pHLA ligand discovery.** Candidate drug-modified peptides are identified by HLA peptidomics of drug-exposed cells bearing the risk allele. Peptide–HLA tetramers confirm binding by the lesion-enriched clonotypes.
3. **Cross-recognition testing.** The same clonotypes are tested for recognition of candidate viral peptides (e.g., HSV, VZV, or EBV epitopes restricted by the same HLA allele) using tetramer staining, cytotoxicity assays, or activation readouts.
4. **Orthogonal confirmation.** Candidate cross-reactive peptides must be confirmed to be naturally processed and presented on the relevant cell types (keratinocytes for SJS/TEN; hepatocytes for DILI) under physiologic conditions. Independent biophysical confirmation of dual recognition by the same TCR would further strengthen the finding.

Scalable TCR synthesis and epitope-discovery screening platforms⁵⁶ now permit systematic mapping of TCR-to-antigen specificities, making high-throughput cross-reactivity testing feasible. Prospective cohorts that combine viral serostatus, HLA genotype, ERAP genotype, and drug-challenge outcomes can test whether the predicted risk factors are jointly necessary.

S9.2 What reduced animal systems can test

- **HLA-transgenic mice** (e.g., the HLA-B*57:01 abacavir model²⁴) can test whether drug-modified peptidomes generate T cells that cross-react with viral peptides restricted by the same HLA.
- **Murine CMV models** can test whether prior viral imprinting biases T-cell responses to a subsequent neoantigen challenge and whether the temporal sequence matters.
- **Humanized mouse models** can reconstitute human TCR–pHLA interactions in a controlled background, permitting direct testing of human clonotype cross-reactivity.

S9.3 What animal models cannot recapitulate

- **Immune receptor polymorphism.** Inbred mice lack the HLA, KIR, and NKG2 diversity that defines human disease susceptibility.
- **Natural viral acquisition.** Under standard laboratory conditions, mice do not naturally transmit murine CMV; infection requires artificial inoculation.
- **Lifelong co-adaptation.** No animal model recapitulates decades of intermittent herpesvirus reactivation in a polymorphically diverse host.
- **Multi-gate causality.** Testing whether a disease requires the simultaneous satisfaction of multiple independent variable conditions requires the genetic and viral diversity of human populations.

These limitations underscore why human lesion-based and cohort-based approaches remain the primary validation path.

S10. Supplementary Figures

Two mechanistic regimes that produce "peripheral tolerance" outcomes: blockade vs thresholding

Figure S1. Two regulatory regimes that can produce clinical tolerance: priming-stage blockade versus tissue-level thresholding.

(A) Priming-stage blockade operates at costimulatory checkpoints, where antigen recognition occurs but clonal expansion and durable competence are constrained. **(B)** Tissue-level thresholding operates within barrier niches containing TRM; inhibitory receptors impose local gain control so that competent TRM remain poised yet restrained until net signaling exceeds the local inhibitory set-point. **(C)** In a drug-dependent mimicry scenario, a step-change in composite pHLA signaling may breach the threshold, converting poised restraint into rapid cytotoxicity.

Figure S2. Routes to drug antigenicity converge on tissue-level threshold breach.

Overview of how distinct chemical routes to drug antigenicity converge on shared tissue-level pathophysiology. **Top left:** HLA co-dominant inheritance and antigen processing shape the peptide–HLA landscape. **Top right (Signal 1):** three models of drug antigenicity: (1) hapten/prohapten (covalent adduct on self peptide); (2) altered peptide repertoire (e.g., abacavir: non-covalent drug binding shifts presented self-peptides); (3) non-covalent drug-dependent recognition (e.g., carbamazepine SJS/TEN: reversible drug interaction creates a transient antigenic surface). **Bottom left (Signal 2):** tissue equilibrium gate with local inhibitory pathways setting an activation threshold. **Bottom middle:** tissue-resident memory niche matching. **Bottom right:** integrated model in which sufficient net signaling breaches inhibitory set-points, enabling rapid tissue recall and tissue-specific injury.

Abbreviations: HLA, human leukocyte antigen; TCR, T-cell receptor; APC, antigen-presenting cell; TRM, tissue-resident memory T cell; SJS/TEN, Stevens–Johnson syndrome/toxic epidermal necrolysis.

“Immune calibration in natural vs modern environments”

A Natural / ancestral calibration

B Modern disrupted calibration

Figure S3. Exposure timing: immune calibration in different epidemiologic settings. In settings with earlier acquisition of persistent infections, immune development may be shaped through structured imprinting. In modern settings, delayed acquisition of persistent viruses and reduced early-life microbial diversity may alter immune calibration. **Important:** this figure illustrates possible rare immune tradeoffs among individuals who survive and thrive under modern conditions. The overwhelming population-level benefits of modern sanitation, vaccination, antibiotics, safer childbirth, shelter, and nutrition are not in question and are not criticized by this model.